

EVALUATION METHOD OF ENGLISH DISTANCE TEACHING QUALITY IN ONLINE EDUCATION PLATFORM

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Abstract:

The current era of society is one of technology and information explosion. Both of them complement one other well and are significantly improving our lives overall, including the crucial area of education, of course. The aforementioned elements have altered the way individuals gain knowledge, and as network science and technology have advanced, people may now easily and quickly access a vast amount of information. Furthermore, systematic learning outside of the classroom is made feasible by the features of the Internet's data transmission.

Key words: distance teaching, education platform, (MAGDM), GDM methods, SNGDM method.

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This study suggests designing methods of evaluation for English distant teaching quality on platforms for distance learning in order to increase the accuracy of such assessments. This method first establishes the selection principle for the English distance education quality evaluation index, chooses the appropriate English distance education quality evaluation index, decides on the evaluation index information collection method, processes the information that has been collected, and uses the analytic hierarchy process to calculate the relative importance of the distance education quality evaluation index. Eventually, the assessment of English distance teaching quality is realized by the use of the weighted average approach, which provides the evaluation result. According to the experimental results, the greatest possible signal-to-noise ratio and integrity of the distance teaching quality assessment index, respectively, are 95.46% and 96%, respectively. The fact that the evaluation of the quality of distant education matches the actual results indicates that the approach suggested in this research operates well in practice. How to Assess the Quality of English Distance Education on an Internet-Based Learning Platform. This study suggests designing assessment techniques for English distant teaching quality on online education platforms in order to increase the accuracy of such assessments. This approach first establishes the determination principle for the English distance education quality evaluation index, chooses the appropriate English distance education quality evaluation index, decides on the evaluation index information collection method, processes the information that has been collected, and uses the analytic hierarchy process to calculate the weight of the online educational quality evaluation index At last, the measurement of English

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distance instruction quality is accomplished by the use of the weighted average procedure, which delivers the evaluation result. According to the experimental results, the highest possible proportion of signal to noise and integrity of the distance teaching quality assessment index, accordingly, are 95.46% and 96%, respectively. The fact that the evaluation of the quality of distant education reflects the actual results indicates that the approach suggested in this research performs well in practice. [1]

Learning through the internet continues to rise in importance in today's educational system, and in order to raise the bar for the sector as a whole, it is vital to assess the efficacy of online instruction. A common multi-attribute group decision-making (MAGDM) problem is the evaluation of online teaching quality, and decision makers might describe the evaluation index using linguistic term sets. In particular, multi-granularity probabilistic the language term sets accomplished from multiple decision makers are better suited to convey complicated ambiguous evaluation information. These sets can not only offer distinct language term sets for various decision makers expressing their preferences, but also capture the relative importance of individual language terms. [4] In this project, we put forward a function for transformation of multi-granularity probabilistic linguistic term sets based on proportional 2-tuple fuzzy linguistic representation model, based on the benefits of multi-granularity probabilistic the language term sets. The comparison rules and operational laws of multi-granularity probabilistic linguistic word sets are provided on the basis of this framework. Next, we create a novel Choquet integral operator for probabilistic linguistic term sets with multiple granularities that takes into account the correlation between characteristics. This operator minimizes the need to account for the normalization stage of the probabilistic linguistic term sets and effectively prevents the loss of evaluation information. Concurrently, the properties of the demonstrated operator are also demonstrated. Furthermore, we propose a new multi-attribute group decision-making method based on the new operator, and analyze the effectiveness of the proposed method by online teaching quality evaluation. Finally, by comparing with some existing methods, the advantages of the proposed method are shown. [3]

At present, there are many GDM methods for teaching quality evaluation, but most of them do not consider the influence of trust networks among experts on the evaluation results. This study extends the SNA method to the GDM method and proposes a new SNGDM method based on q-ROFS for the evaluation of online teaching quality, which makes the evaluation results more reasonable.

Emotion Recognition System From Multiple Perspectives

Subsequently individuals are the highest human beings on the planet, one of their characteristics is the capacity to express emotion. By recognizing human emotions, one can learn a great deal and develop a deeper understanding of the individual. [5] This article examines the relationship between emotional identification and language learning—that is, the process of developing a more profound understanding of students—in order to create a teaching model. It has also become necessary to conduct research on the recognition of emotions from various angles.

Introduction to the Process of Facial Emotional Recognition

There are many ways to express human emotions. The first is to introduce the emotion recognition technology of human face and related principles. Face

emotion recognition can be achieved by deep learning algorithms in the current environment. The process features are the same as the description. Facial Emotion Recognition Extraction Method for the realization of facial emotion recognition technology, the most important thing is the ability to extract the features of the human face that can best represent the emotion of the person at that time. [2]

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